

PHARMACOEPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMED CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH CHOLELITHIASIS OF THE GERONTOLOGICAL GROUP OF ANDIJAN

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Relevance. According to the WHO, in the modern treatment and diagnostic process of cholelithiasis (CSD) it is important, especially in individuals of the gerontological group (75-90 years and above), not only to provide scientific information on a certain type of treatment (surgical or conservative) and clinical and fundamental recommendations, but also to acquire modern innovative technologies acceptable for preventive surgery and the ability to use them. For the advanced development of CSD surgery in the 21st century, it is important to identify the most susceptible individuals with high or very high risk for this pathology and their special prevention to ensure the process of early detection, effective and safe treatment (with proper pharmacovigilance, pharmacoepidemiological screening) and the prevention of not only CSD itself, but also formidable complications of cholecystectomy, cholecystostomy, choledochotomy, choledochomyotomy and transduodenal sphincteropylotomy.

The aim of the study is to study the prevalence, pharmacoepidemiology of cholelithiasis and its main risk factors among the male and female unorganized population of the gerontological group of the Fergana Valley to enable scientifically based planning and optimization of early diagnosis, prevention and treatment of this disease.

The object of the study was a contingent of 4,500 individuals of the gerontological age population, formed using random number tables based on the nominal electoral lists of men and women in three regions of the Fergana Valley; as well as 779 patients with cholelithiasis who were undergoing inpatient treatment in the regional multidisciplinary hospitals of Andijan, Namangan and Fergana (for VEN analysis).

The subject of the study: were the results of general clinical and biochemical blood tests, survey, physical, instrumental and

pharmacoepidemiological monitoring; as well as the method of "daily nutrition reproduction" adapted to the peculiarities of Uzbek cuisine.

Research methods. To solve the set tasks, epidemiological, clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental, pharmacoepidemiological and statistical research methods were used, as well as the "daily nutrition reproduction" method.

Results of the study pharmacoepidemiological analysis of the performed conservative treatment in patients with cholelithiasis of the gerontological group of Andijan.

Conservative strategy is used in 11.1% of men and 88.9% of women with cholelithiasis of the gerontological group of Andijan.

It is noted that antihypertensive therapy is used in 1.39% of men and 6.9% of women, i.e. in 8.3% of cases in patients of gerontological age of Andijan with cholelithiasis conservative therapy is used ($\chi^2=0.741$; $P>0.05$; $RR=1.800$; 95% $CI=1.003-3.229$). Antispasmodics are used in 13.9% of cases, in 1.39% of men and 12.5% of women with cholelithiasis ($\chi^2=12.80$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.111$; 95% $CI=0.017-0.722$). In the group of patients $\geq 60 - 90$ years old, men and women with cholelithiasis, analgesics are taken by 13.9%, 1.39% and 12.5%, respectively ($\chi^2=12.80$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.11$; 95% $CI=0.017-0.722$). Similar indicators regarding the use of antibacterial drugs, enzyme inhibitors, infusion agents and anticoagulants are confirmed in the treatment of cholelithiasis in gerontologically aged individuals in Andijan ($\chi^2=12.80$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.111$; 95% $CI=0.017-0.722$).

As a conservative therapy for cholelithiasis, NSAIDs are used in 4.2% of cases, in 1.39% of men and in 2.8% of women $\geq 60 - 90$ years with cholelithiasis ($\chi^2=2.593$; $P>0.05$; $RR=4.500$; 95% $CI=1.326-15.28$). In patients with cholelithiasis, proton inhibitors are used with a frequency of 1.39%, 12.5%, and 13.9%, respectively, in men, women, and the entire population $\geq 60-90$ years of age in the Andijan region.

In general, in the gerontological group of the population with cholelithiasis in Andijan, the basic drug therapy conducted in 97.0% of cases corresponds to modern international recommendations, its gender difference is insignificant – it is observed only in 3.0% of cases

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